

INFLUENCE OF TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF PLASMA CUTTING AT STRAIGHT POLARITY WITH THE ADDITIVE OF WATER TO THE PLASMA-FORMING GAS ON THE QUALITY OF CUT EDGES

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Abstract

The work is devoted to determining the degree of influence of technological parameters of plasma cutting in direct polarity with plasma-forming media air and oxygen on the quality of the edges of the resulting cut. It has been established that the main approach to reducing the non-perpendicularity of edges when plasma cutting metals at straight polarity is the choice of mode parameters that ensure the minimum amount of non-perpendicularity at the maximum cutting speed. It is necessary to take into account that with an increase in cutting speed (from 16.7 to 50 mm/s), the non-perpendicularity of the edges increases (about 2 times), and with an increase in the consumption of the plasma-forming medium (air, oxygen), the non-perpendicularity decreases. Increasing the cutting speed leads to a decrease in the immersion depth of the anode spot and uneven heat release throughout the thickness of the part. An increase in the consumption of the plasma-forming medium increases the compression of the arc, which increases its energy characteristics and contributes to the immersion of the anode spot throughout the thickness of the metal. At the same time, the width of the cut on the lower edge increases, which reduces the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges for thicknesses of 5...12 mm by approximately 2.0-2.5 times.

Keywords: plasma cutting, straight polarity, plasma-forming media, flow rate, water addition, cutting speed, anode spot, non-perpendicularity of edges, roughness, non-perpendicularity angle.

One of the most common methods for producing flat metal workpieces is air plasma cutting with direct polarity [1]. In plasma cutting, an arc burns between a non-consumable cathode electrode and the metal being cut (direct arc). The arc column is combined with a high-speed plasma jet, which is formed from plasma-

forming air due to its heating and ionization under the action of a compressed electric arc. For cutting, the energy of the anode spot of the electric arc, the arc column and the flowing plasma-forming nozzle of the plasma torch is used (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Scheme of the air plasma cutting process on straight polarity:
 1 – electrode-cathode; 2 – body; 3 – insulator; 4 – forming tip; 5 – arc chamber; 6 – arc column;
 7 – supply of plasma-forming gas; 8 – cooling water supply; 9 – water drain; 10 – current source;
 11 – arc ignition device; 12 – metal to be cut; 13 – cutting direction.

However, this method has a number of characteristic disadvantages. Disadvantages associated with wear of the cathode electrode can be eliminated by adding water to the plasma-forming air. This technique also increases cutting intensity and reduces edge roughness [2]. However, not all defects can be eliminated in this way. Analysis of characteristic defects of the cut surface shows that the main ones are [3]: non-parallelism of the cut edges and deviation of the cut axis from the normal to the plane of the sheet being cut, causing asymmetry of the edges. These defects are a consequence of the heat flux intensity varying across the thickness of the metal.

The purpose of the work is to determine the degree of influence of technological parameters of plasma cutting in direct polarity with plasma-forming media air and oxygen on the quality of the edges of the resulting cut.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were

solved: determining the influence of plasma cutting speed and plasma-forming medium consumption on the non-perpendicularity of edges; determining the influence of the composition and consumption of the plasma-forming medium on the condition of the edges; influence on the non-perpendicularity of the edges by the rotation of the gas flow; determining the influence of the thickness of the metal being cut on the angular value of the non-perpendicularity of the edges.

Statistical processing of the results of studies of the side edges of parts after plasma cutting showed that the average value of non-perpendicularity $\Delta = 2.5$ mm with a dispersion $S = 1.5$ mm (Fig. 2). If B_1 is the width of the cut along the upper edge of the cut, and B_2 is along the lower edge, then the amount of non-perpendicularity Δ is determined by the equation:

$$\Delta = \frac{B_1 - B_2}{2} \tag{1}$$

Fig. 2. Non-perpendicularity of cut edges.

Thermal energy is most intensely localized in the anode spot [4, 5]. In [6], based on the results of oscillography of currents when cutting a batch sample with insulated sheets, it was concluded that the active arc spot during the cutting process can move along the height of the front wall from the top edge to the bottom and back. In [7], using high-speed filming methods, the mechanism of shunting the anode spot of an arc with an axial gas flow excited on the surface of a water-cooled copper anode tangential to the arc column was studied. It has been determined that the spot moves only in one direction, from top to bottom, and an increase in the distance from the plate surface to the burner axis increases the range of shunting and arc voltage pulsation. In this case, the shunt zone moves downstream.

Some characteristics of arc pulsation were obtained by high-speed filming with synchronous oscillography of the parameters of this arc, stabilized on a tangential non-consumable anode [8]. In the same work, in the process of cutting carbon steel samples, the intensity of arc radiation was measured through the cutting slot using a photocell and a recording device. Assuming that the observed brightness pulsation corresponds to the movement of the anode spot, it is suggested that during the cutting process the anode spot behaves in the same way as when an arc burns on a copper plate.

The spot on the surface of the metal edge moves periodically, the voltage pulsates with a frequency from several kilohertz to tens of kHz. The spot moves due to the momentum of the plasma flow, cold surrounding gas and magnetic forces [9].

It is noted that in real cutting conditions the process is complicated by metal melting. In practice, there are cases when several anode spots simultaneously exist between the upper and lower parts of the cut cavity.

The anode spot of the cutting arc, resulting from the breakdown of the gas layer between the arc column and the frontal surface of the cut, slides to the lower edges of the cut. As sliding occurs at the upper edges, a shunt breakdown occurs with the formation of the upper radial section and the disappearance of the lower one. The sliding speed of the anode spot is 200-500 m/s [10].

The immersion depth of the anode spot is related to the cutting speed. At the minimum VPR speed, the anode spot reaches the lower edge of the cut, the edges remain parallel for steel 12 mm thick at a speed of 9.5 mm/s. As the cutting speed is further reduced, the width of the cut at the bottom increases compared to the top of the cut edges.

The cutting width of plasma cutting exceeds the width of laser and oxy-acetylene cutting. The obtained experimental dependencies show that the width of the cut during VPR is 1.5-2 times the diameter of the nozzle along the upper edge of the cut. The width along the lower edge depends on the cutting speed limit and is equal to 1.5-2.0 mm.

The non-parallelism of the cut edges is affected by the voltage on the arc, the composition and consumption of the plasma-forming medium, the current strength, and the distance between the plasma torch and the metal, however, the influence of these parameters compared to the cutting speed has less influence.

The values we obtained for the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges when changing the air plasma cutting speed are given in Table 1 for carbon steel 8 mm thick at a plasma gas flow rate of 90 l/min and a nozzle diameter of 3 mm. The denominator shows the average values of cut width and non-perpendicularity for 5 samples. From Table 1 it can be seen that with increasing cutting speed, the non-perpendicularity of the edges increases.

Table 1.

Dependence of non-perpendicularity of cut edges on air plasma cutting speed.

No	Plasma-forming medium	Cutting speed, mm/s	Cutting width, mm		Δ , mm
			along the upper edges	along the bottom edges	
1	Air	16,6	6,0-6,7 / 6,18	3,5-4,5 / 4,02	0,8-1,25 / 1,08
2		33,3	5,5-6,2 / 5,92	3,0-3,6 / 3,28	1,2-1,45 / 1,32
3		50	5,8-6,3 / 6,02	2,4-3,6 / 2,78	1,4-1,95 / 1,62

The influence of the consumption of the plasma-forming medium on the quality of cutting can be seen from Table 2 and Fig. 3. An increase in the flow rate of the plasma-forming medium (air and oxygen) leads to a decrease in the non-perpendicularity of the edges, for example, an increase in gas flow from 0.67 to 2.5 l/s reduces the non-perpendicularity of the edges for air

from 2.25 to 1.75, and for oxygen - from 1.95 to 1.15. This nature of the influence of gas flow is explained by the fact that in plasmatrons with tangential gas supply into the nozzle channel, an increase in its flow leads to greater compression of the arc [11]. The change in gas flow was ensured by a change in its pressure.

Table 2.

Dependence of the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges on the consumption of the plasma-forming medium (average values from 5 samples).

No	Plasma-forming medium	Plasma flow rate, l/s	Cutting speed, mm/s	Cutting width, mm		Δ , mm
				along the upper edges	along the bottom edges	
1	Air	0,67	41,7	6,7	2,2	2,25
2	- " -	1,33	41,7	6,2	2,4	1,9
3	- " -	2,0	41,7	6,0	2,4	1,8
4	- " -	2,5	41,7	6,0	2,5	1,75
5	Oxygen	0,67	41,7	5,4	2,5	1,4
6	- " -	1,33	41,7	5,0	2,5	1,25
7	- " -	2,0	41,7	4,9	2,5	1,2
8	- " -	2,5	41,7	4,8	2,5	1,15

Fig. 3. Dependence of the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges Δ [mm] on the flow rate of the plasma-forming medium Q [l/s]: Δ – air; \circ – oxygen.

It has been established that the magnitude of non-perpendicularity is not stable under the same conditions and depends on the shape of the plasma column. In case of poor quality machining of the nozzle, misalignment of the nozzle and the cathode insert of the electrode, the shape of the plasma jet differs from cylindrical and when cutting in coordinate axes, the shape of the cut is different. Therefore, special attention must be paid to the processing and cleanliness of the nozzle.

Experiments showed that adding 0.028...0.11 l/min of water to the plasma improved the quality of the cut edges and reduced their non-perpendicularity. The cut surface had a silver color and a slight roughness of the edge surface (Fig. 4). When water is added, the edge roughness is $R_z = 0.020...0.010$ mm; when cutting in a clean air environment, $R_z = 0.12...0.09$ mm, i.e., the roughness with the addition of water decreases by 6...9 times and corresponds to the first class according to EN ISO 9013.

Based on the results of modeling the composition of the gas phase, the vapor concentrations in the plasma were approximately selected to be 10...20%. Based on the distribution of water supplied to the plasmatron

nozzle, these concentrations provide a total water flow into the internal channels of the nozzle of 0.023...0.11 l/min or 0.082...0.4 l/min of water into the nozzle. The effect of such additives was studied on the non-perpendicularity of cut edges.

It has been established that adding water to the plasma flow from 0.028 to 0.11 l/min (5.6...19.2% steam in the plasma) reduces the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges from 2.3...2.5 mm to ≤ 1.0 mm, which corresponds to the second class according to EN ISO 9013 for thicknesses 5...12 mm.

Two factors contribute to reducing the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges: the formation of gas mixtures with hydrogen, which increases the electric field strength of the arc, and compression of the plasma arc. The arc voltage increases by 25...30 V at a constant current value. Compression of the arc increases its energy characteristics and contributes to the immersion of the anode spot throughout the thickness of the metal. This is evidenced by an increase in the width of the cut at the lower edge. The non-perpendicularity of cut edges of different thicknesses is reduced by 2.3...2.5 times.

Fig. 4. The surface of the edges after plasma cutting of steel; plasma-forming medium: 1 – air; 2 – air + water.

It has been established that the non-perpendicularity of the right and left edges of the cut is different and depends on the direction of rotation of the plasma flow [4].

In existing plasmatrons with vortex stabilization, the spatial stabilization of the arc is determined by the aerodynamic characteristics of the swirling gas flow. Numerous studies of vortex devices indicate the existence of tangential and axial components of the gas flow velocity in the vortex. The radial section of the arc is subject to movement, which is determined not only by the axial component of the velocity, but also by the circumferential one. The features of the influence of this component on the movement of the closing section of the arc were determined in [12]. It has been established that the average speed of movement of the radial section of the arc for a non-consumable anode is close to the circumferential speed of the gas at this radius. The radial section of the arc is shaped like a spiral with a convexity facing the direction of gas movement.

The movement of the anode spot in the cutting cavity, in contrast to movement in cylindrical electrodes, is limited to half of the cylinder, since the other half is removed from the cutting cavity. The radial section of the cutting arc with the anode spot moves in two mutually perpendicular directions: in the direction of the axial z component of the cutting arc and in the direction of the tangential y component of the vortex flow

Fig. 5. Scheme of movement of the anode spot in the horizontal section of the cut: a) – frontal section of the cutting channel; b) – top view of the channel.

Plasma torches used in industry have a right-handed swirl cutter, which ensures right-hand rotation of the gas flow, while the heat transfer to the right edge in the direction of movement of the plasma torch is greater and its non-perpendicularity is less than to the left. If plasma cutting of metal is performed to the left, counterclockwise, i.e. The cut part remains on the left side; if you look in the direction of movement of the plasma torch, then the amount of non-perpendicularity appears to be greater on the part. To measure the

(Fig. 5). If we take into account that the metal is removed during the cutting process, forming a cutting cavity behind the arc, and the frontal edge of the cut, compared to the thickness of the metal being cut, can be an order of magnitude smaller, then the curvature of this section can be replaced by a straight line, and the direction of intersection of the radial section along this line can be taken for W_{er} . It can be assumed that under real cutting conditions the resulting speed W_{er} will be equal to the sum of two vectors: axial W_z and radial W_y

$$\overline{W_{er}} = \overline{W_z} + \overline{W_y} \quad (2)$$

From equation (2) it is easy to calculate the angle of deviation of the cutting axis from the normal

$$\alpha = \arctg \frac{\overline{W_y}}{\overline{W_z}} \quad (3)$$

The arc is shunted from the side of the edge corresponding to the downward tangential component of the vortex flow. The resulting anodic section, as a result of gas-dynamic action, moves to the opposite side of the cut. In this case, the supporting section of the arc makes a diagonal movement along the frontal surface of the cut from the upper part of the left edge to the lower part of the right edge, which is one of the reasons for the resulting asymmetry of heat transfer to the edges of the plasma cut during vortex stabilization of the arc.

amount of non-perpendicularity in the right and left edges of the cut, parts were cut out in 5 pieces. clockwise and counterclockwise. The width of the parts was measured from the front and back sides. Half of the difference in part dimensions is the non-perpendicularity of the right and left cut edges. The measurement results showed that the amount of non-perpendicularity on the left edge is 20-25% higher than on the right. To obtain the minimum amount of non-perpendicularity of the

edges of the parts, it is advisable to perform plasma cutting clockwise (with the gas flow swirling to the right in the plasmatron), the part should remain to the right in relation to the cutting direction.

The non-perpendicularity of the cut edges increases with increasing metal thickness and cutting speed, which is associated with the location of the anode spot in the cut cavity.

When plasma cutting, it is not advisable to reduce non-perpendicularity by reducing the cutting speed, as this will lead to an increase in the width of the cut, the appearance of deformations in the cut parts and a decrease in productivity. The main direction of reducing non-perpendicularity is the choice of cutting conditions that provide a minimum value of non-perpendicularity

with high productivity.

Change in the total water flow into the plasma torch nozzle (1.67...3.3) 10⁻³ l/s when cutting in a plasma-forming medium oxygen + water and (1.67...4.67) 10⁻³ l/s when cutting in the air + water environment, the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges practically did not change. An increase in the flow rate of the plasma-forming medium without changing the water flow rate leads to a decrease in the non-perpendicularity of the edges for the air + water medium from 1.3 to 0.83; oxygen + water from 1.5 to 0.65. Data on the amount of non-perpendicularity of the edges depending on the flow rate of the plasma-forming medium are given in Table 3 and Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Dependence of the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges on the flow rate of the plasma-forming gas: plasma-forming medium: ▲ – air + water; ● – oxygen + water.

Table 3.

Dependence of edge non-perpendicularity on the consumption of plasma-forming medium when cutting 8 mm thick steel.

No	Plasma-forming medium	Consumption of plasma-forming medium, l/s	Water consumption, x10 ⁻³ l/s	Cutting speed, mm/s	Cutting width, mm		Amount of non-perpendicularity, mm	
					at the top	at the bottom		
1	Air + water	0,83	4,6...5,6	33,3	6,3-6,5	3,6-3,8	1,2-1,45	
2		1,33			6,4	3,7	1,3	
3		2,0			5,8-6,3	4,0-4,2	0,8-1,15	
4	Oxygen + water	0,83	3,0...3,6		5,5-5,85	3,65-4,0	0,75-1,1	
5					1,33	5,9-6,3	2,8-3,1	1,4-1,75
6					2,0	5,9-6,25	3,95-4,4	0,75-1,15
					6,0	4,1	1,0	
					5,7	3,9	0,9	
					6,1	3,0	1,5	
					6,0	4,2	0,9	
					5,0-5,8	4,0-4,3	0,5-0,75	
					5,5	4,2	0,6	

Increasing the cutting speed leads to an increase in the non-perpendicularity of the edges from 0.5 to 1.1 mm for the plasma-forming medium air + water and from 0.4 to 0.9 mm for the medium oxygen + water.

The obtained dependence of the non-perpendicularity of the edges on the cutting speed when cutting 5 parts 250x50 mm is shown in Table 4 and Fig. 7.

Table 4.

Dependence of edge non-perpendicularity on the cutting speed of 8 mm thick steel.

No	Plasma-forming medium	Consumption of plasma-forming medium, l/s	Water consumption, $\times 10^{-3}$ l/s	Cutting speed, mm/s	The amount of non-perpendicularity in the edges, mm		Average value of non-perpendicularity, mm
					right	left	
1	Air + water	1,3...1,5	4,6...5,6	16,7	0,35-0,6 0,44	0,45-0,8 0,56	0,4-0,7 0,5
2				33,3	0,7-1,2 0,83	0,92-1,6 1,07	0,8-1,3 0,95
3				50,0	0,72-1,2 0,95	1,0-1,44 1,24	0,85-1,3 1,1
4	Oxygen + water	1,5...1,6	3,0...3,3	16,7	0,3-0,45 0,35	0,4...0,55 0,45	0,35-0,5 0,4
5				33,3	0,4-0,74 0,6	0,56-0,8 0,7	0,5-0,8 0,65
6				50,0	0,6-1,25 0,8	0,8-1,25 1,00	0,7-1,15 0,9

Fig. 7. Dependence of non-perpendicularity of cut edges on cutting speed, plasma-forming medium:

▲ – air + water; ● – oxygen + water.

The angular value of the non-perpendicularity depends on the thickness of the metal being cut. As the thickness increases, the angle of non-perpendicularity decreases. The resulting dependence of non-perpendicularity on metal thickness is given in Table 5 and shown in Fig. 8. The amount of non-perpendicularity of the cut edges is mainly influenced by the cutting speed. Increasing the cutting speed leads to a decrease in the immersion depth of the anode spot and uneven heat release throughout the thickness of the part.

Fig. 8. Dependence of the bevel angle of the edges on the thickness of the metal: Δ – air; \blacktriangle – air + water.

Table 5.

Dependence of the bevel angle of the edges on the thickness of the metal.

No	Thickness of cut metal, mm	Consumption of plasma-forming medium, l/s	Cutting speed, mm/s	Bevel of edges, deg.	
				Air	Air + water
1	8	1,3...1,5	38,3	9-11 10	5-8 7
2	12		25,0	6-8 7	3-6 5
3	16		20,0	5-7 6,5	3-5 3,5
4	20		15,0	4,5-7 5,5	2-4 3
5	24		11,6	4-6 5	2-3,5 2,5
6	28		6,6	3,5-5 4,5	2-3 2,5

The plasma cutting process is based on melting metal from the cut cavity. Due to the rapid movement of a point source of heat relative to the surface of the metal being cut, a large temperature difference is observed in a relatively narrow area adjacent to the cut surface. As a result, processes occur at the edges of the metal, accompanied by changes in the chemical composition, structure and mechanical properties of the metal.

Conclusions.

1. It has been established that the main approach to reducing the non-perpendicularity of edges when plasma cutting metals at straight polarity is the choice of mode parameters that ensure the minimum amount of non-perpendicularity at the maximum cutting speed. It is necessary to take into account that with an increase in cutting speed (from 16.7 to 50 mm/s), the non-perpendicularity of the edges increases (about 2 times), and with an increase in the consumption of the plasma-

forming medium (air, oxygen), the non-perpendicularity decreases. Increasing the cutting speed leads to a decrease in the immersion depth of the anode spot and uneven heat release throughout the thickness of the part. An increase in the consumption of the plasma-forming medium increases the compression of the arc, which increases its energy characteristics and contributes to the immersion of the anode spot throughout the thickness of the metal. At the same time, the width of the cut on the lower edge increases, which reduces the non-perpendicularity of the cut edges for thicknesses of 5...12 mm by approximately 2.0-2.5 times.

2. It has been established that when water is added to the plasma-forming medium (to form 10-20% water vapor), the roughness of the cut edges decreases by 6-9 times, and their non-perpendicularity decreases by approximately 2.0-2.5 times for thicknesses of 5...12 mm. An increase in the flow rate of the plasma-forming medium (air, oxygen) by 1.5-2.0 times without changing

the water flow rate leads to a decrease in the non-perpendicularity of the edges by 2-6 times.

3. Plasma torches used in industry usually have a right-handed swirl cutter, which ensures right-hand rotation of the gas flow, while the heat transfer to the right edge in the direction of movement of the plasma torch is greater and its non-perpendicularity is 20-25% less than to the left. To minimize the non-perpendicularity of the edges of the cut parts, it is advisable to perform plasma cutting clockwise (with the gas flow swirling to the right in the plasmatron), the part should remain to the right in relation to the cutting direction.

4. It has been established that the angular value of non-perpendicularity decreases with increasing thickness of the metal being cut. For example, when the metal thickness increases from 8 to 20 mm, the angular value of non-perpendicularity during air plasma cutting decreases by approximately a factor of 20. In this case, the addition of water to the plasma-forming medium further reduces the angular value of non-perpendicularity by approximately 1.5 times.

Gratitude.

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